

ROLE OF COLLOCATIONS IN LANGUAGE SYSTEM AND SPEECH

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***Abstract.** English collocations are a considerable part of the English language. Collocations are commonly used in English speech and writing and are considered an indispensable factor in the proficiency of the learners of English. Acquiring collocations is crucial, challenging, and problematic to non-native English speakers. In this article, firstly we give definitions to the term “collocation”, and classify them according to semantic and grammatical features.*

***Key words:** collocation, semantic feature, grammatical feature, speech, language proficiency, chunk.*

The term "*collocation*" has a long history, and Firth first mentioned it in 1957 as “a word by the company it keeps. On account of its perceived role in vocabulary mastery as well as in the learners' fluency in English, many linguists attempted to define this term from different perspectives”.

For example, Nation (1990) gave a morphological analysis of collocation based on its constituents in which '*col*' means 'together'; '*-loc-*' means 'to place or put.'

Meanwhile, Haliday and Hasan (1976) consider collocation as 'lexical cohesion,' which is the cohesive effect achieved by the selection of the vocabulary. This definition is different from the notions of other linguists.

Celce- Murcia (2000) refers to collocation as" words come together or 'chunks that native speakers can access for comprehension or production'.

Similarly, McCarthy (2008) defines collocations as 'pairs of words that occur regularly together, with a high degree of probability (p.5).

Also, Colin et al. (2019) regard collocation as 'the way words combine in a language to produce natural-sounding speech and writing.' Collocations are classified according to many criteria. Considered the correlation between the **semantic relation** of the words or phrases in context, collocations are divided into:

- strong collocations,
- fixed collocations,
- weak collocations.

In strong collocations, the words are very closely associated with each other. For instance, in the sentence “*she has auburn hair*”, the word **auburn** only collocates with words connected with hair. Fixed collocations are called idioms as mentioned above. Weak collocations consist of words that can collocate with other words. For example, broad can be used with a number of words like *a broad avenue, a broad forehead, a broad smile, a broad hint*, etc.

Concerning the **grammatical feature of collocations**, collocations are commonly classified as follows:

- Adjectives and nouns, e.g., *the key issue, a brief chat, mounting concern*
- Nouns and verbs, e.g., *an opportunity arises, standards slip economy booms*
- Verbs and nouns, e.g., *pose a problem, launch a product, withstand the impact*
- Nouns and nouns, e.g., *a surge of anger, a sense of pride, a flock of birds, a school of fish*
- Verbs and expressions with prepositions, e.g., *fill with sorrow, burst into tears, swell with pride*
- Verbs and adverbs, e.g., *drive recklessly, fail miserably, whisper softly*
- Adverbs and adjectively, e.g., *blissfully unaware, stunningly attractive, utterly ridiculous*.

It is undeniable that each language has its own natural order in which words appear or are put together in sentences or utterances. This is known as collocations in English. Collocations are easy and natural to native speakers but problematic to

language learners. The reason for this problem is understandable. In Swan’s words, “Language of this kind is notoriously challenging for learners”.

Admittedly, English learners spend years learning a vast stock of vocabulary and grammar rules, but still, their speech and writing do not belong to the so-called native-like selection. It has been observed that such collocations as *"feel headache"* or *"feel stomachache"*, *"drink some medicine"*, *"a fast lunch"*, *"problems happen"*, *"She has yellow hair"*, *"We are meeting many difficulties"*, *"She smiled with me"*, *"Me very like music"*, *"I often go to eat in a restaurant near my school"* and so on are commonly used by Uzbek learners. These would probably be understandable, but they are not what would naturally be said in English. It is proved by Liu (1999), Hsu (2004), Tang (2004), Mahmoud (2005), Shitu (2015), Phoocharoensil (2011), Shih (2000) that deficiency in knowledge of collocations and the mother tongue interference mostly account for the errors in collocations. We did an investigation on mistakes related to collocations that Uzbek students make in their speech.

Figure 1. Common errors in English collocations of Uzbek learners

Wrong	Correct
A fast lunch	A quick lunch
A fast growth	A rapid growth
A golden chance	A golden opportunity
A strong car engine	A powerful car engine
Catch the chance	Take the chance
Drink a medicine	Take a medicine
Feel headache	Have headache
Do the preparation	Make the preparation
Make research	Do research

These errors are worth considering since they offered supporting evidence to the reviewed literature about the nature of errors. As we can see that 'medicine' does not go with 'drink'; and 'do research' not 'do research', or 'make the preparation' rather

than 'do the preparation'. In these cases, the students would probably transfer the equivalent Uzbek lexical phrases to English collocation due to the unfamiliarity with the English collocations. English is not considered as ordinary, natural, or fluent without the competence in collocations. In other words, a learner needs to gain adequate knowledge of collocations and use them properly in communication so as to be fluent and native-like.

The results from many studies have proved that acquiring collocations is an integral part of achieving proficiency. Therefore, good teaching materials should comprise collocations and provide a variety of examples and practice in using collocations. Especially in Uzbek context, collocations should be included in the textbooks and teaching materials so that the teachers and students can explore and absorb the collocations and the learners can gradually improve their knowledge and language skills as collocations are not easy to master for second or foreign language learners. Above all, in the language class, teachers should convey the significance of the acquisition of collocations and give learners repeated exposure to typical collocations in spoken and written texts.

Conclusion

Collocations are an important aspect of language acquisition. Knowledge and the use of collocations contribute to the improvement of four skills. It is widely known that fluency depends greatly on collocations. Errors in collocations indicate that many students lack the knowledge of collocations, which impacts fluency. Therefore, collocations should be included in the syllabus of schools. As English teachers, we should find out the best ways to instruct students with collocations and provide sufficient practice to acquire collocations effectively. As fluency is the goal that language learners make an effort to achieve, collocations are considered a useful tool to reach that goal.

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